

Updates from School of Science and Technology

Sn.	Event/Program	Semester	Number of Participants	Start Date	End Date	Remarks
1	Basic Hardware and Networking-Workshop	First/2078	48	11 Shrawan	18 Shrawan	Mr. Shubham Bohara
2	Talk Show[Career Counseling Related to IT]	Third and all interested/2077	29	26 Shrawan	26 Shrawan	Er. Pradeep Raj Poudel (Computer Engineer of Ministry of Tourism, Culture and Aviation).
3	Robotics Workshop	All Interested	31	05 Bhadra	05 Bhadra	Mr. Bikrant Karki (Under Robotics Academy of Nepal)
4	AI/MI Workshop	All interested need to register	47	17 Bhadra	17 Bhadra	Fuse Machines.
5	Hardware & Networking Workshop	3rd Semester	24	20 Kartik	20 Kartik	Mr. Shubham Bohara
6	Guest Lecture- Project work	7th Semester	30	28 Mangshir	28 Mangshir	Mr. Bikrant Karki (Robotics Nepal)
7	Project Start up	7th Semester	33	04 Poush	04 Poush	Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra
8	Workshop- Project report writing	7th Semester	31	18 Poush	18 Poush	Mr. Nawaraj Poudel
9	Web 3.0- Guest Lecture	CSIT and BCA Students	67	24th Poush	24th Poush	Mr. Ananda Nepal (Coordinator, Web System Development, The Kyoto College, Japan)
10	Management Workshops	BSC-CSIT 2nd and 4th Sem	40	8th, 15th, 22nd Magh	29th Magh	Mr. Parmeshwor Dahal (Airlines- Airport Services/ Lecturer POM)

1. Basic Hardware and workshop

Computer Hardware & Networking Workshop

**27TH JULY TO
3RD AUGUST**

**FIRST
SEMESTER**

*Venue:
Digital Lab, BSC-CSIT*

Picture 1: Motherboard repair

Picture 2: Inspecting CPU

Picture 3: Teaming up to check hardware

Picture 4: Slide presentation during workshop

2. Talk Show[Career Counseling Related to IT]

TALK SHOW

On
'IT scope & Career Perspective in Nepal'

Guest Speaker:
Mr. Pradip Raj POUDYAL
Computer Engineer
Planning and Evaluation Division, Ministry of Culture, Tourism and Civil Aviation.

Participants:
Third Semester and Interested Students

Thursday	1.00PM	26 Shrawan 2079
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MBM
Madan Bhandari Memorial College

Organized By:
Madan Bhandari Memorial College
BSC-CSIT Department

3. Robotics Workshop

ROBOTICS WORKSHOP

Contents:

A. Conceptual- 1.5Hrs

- Introduction to Robotics.
- Computer and Robotics Basic Concepts

B. Basic Robotics- 1.5Hrs

- Basic Programming Concepts
- IT Concept
- AR and VR Technology
- Drone Technology

SUNDAY 21st AUGUST

START AT 9:00AM

Venue

3rd Floor, Sagarmatha hall-305

Presented By:
Bikrant Karki
Under:

(Robotics Academy of Nepal)
ICT Frame Magazine

Organized By:
BSC-CSIT Department

Picture 5: Starting drone for take off

Picture 6: Slide show on UAV

Picture 7: Group photo with presenters

Picture 8: Student attending workshop

Picture 9: Slide show

Picture 10: Slide Show

4. AI/MI Workshop

The poster features a textured brown background with a pattern of small black dots. At the top right is the MBM logo. The main title 'AI/Machine Learning WORKSHOP' is prominently displayed in blue and purple. Below the title is a list of three bullet points. On the left, there are two vertical panels: one for Artificial Intelligence (blue) and one for Machine Learning (green). A central yellow rounded rectangle contains the text 'Participants: Interested all Students'. At the bottom, a light blue rounded rectangle contains the organizer information. On the right, two white rounded rectangles with icons provide the date and time.

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AI/Machine Learning WORKSHOP

- Knowledge on industry practices in AI/ML pipeline.
- Get connected with Fuse Machines AI engineers/ Networking.
- Provide career counseling.

Artificial Intelligence
Engineering of making Intelligent Machines and Programs

Machine Learning
Ability to learn without being explicitly programmed

Participants:
Interested all Students

Organizer:
BSC CSIT department
Cooperation with Fuse Machines

FRIDAY
02 September

11:00AM
to 4:00PM

Picture 11: Student interaction during slide show

Picture 12: AI/ML workshop slide show

Picture 13: Handing over Token of love to presenter

Picture 14: Students attending workshop

5. Hardware & Networking Workshop

Computer Hardware & Networking Workshop

Venue:
Digital Lab, BSC-CSIT

13TH NOVEMBER & 27TH NOVEMBER

THIRD SEMESTER

schedule

13th Nov: 10:00-12:00 (Roll no. 1-12)
12:00-02:00 (Roll no. 13-24)

27th Nov: 10:00-12:00 (Roll no. 25-36)
12:00-02:00 (Roll no. 37-48)

Picture 15: PATA/SATA slide presentation

Picture 16: Student attending workshop

Picture 17: Slide show

Picture 18: Inspecting motherboard

6. Guest Lecture- Project work

IOT- INTERNET OF THINGS

Guest Lecturer for Project work.

Mr. Bikrant Karki

Under:
(Robotics Academy of Nepal)
ICT Frame Magazine

Participants - 7th Semester, BSc.CSIT

WEDNESDAY 14TH December

START AT 8:30AM

Venue

3rd Floor, Sagarmatha hall-305

**Organized By:
BSC-CSIT Department**

7. Project Start up

A poster for a project start-up event. It features a grey background with red geometric shapes in the corners. At the top left is the MBM logo. A red banner across the top contains the title 'PROJECT- START UP'. Below this, it says 'Organized By: BSC-CSIT Department'. A portrait of Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra, wearing a traditional Nepali hat, is centered. Below the portrait, his name and role are listed. The participants are identified as '7th Semester, BSc.CSIT'. The date 'MONDAY 19TH December' is highlighted in a red box, followed by 'START AT 8:30AM'. The venue '3rd Floor, Sagarmatha hall-305' is also highlighted in a red box.

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PROJECT- START UP

Organized By:
BSC-CSIT Department

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra
Guest Lecturer for
Project work

Participants - 7th Semester, BSc.CSIT

MONDAY 19TH December

START AT 8:30AM

Venue
3rd Floor, Sagarmatha hall-305

8. Workshop- Project report writing

**WORKSHOP
ON
PROJECT REPORT WRITING**

Organized By:
BSc.CSIT Department

Mr. Nawaraj Paudel

Associate Professor, Central Department of CSIT, TU

Participants - 7th Semester, BSc.CSIT

MONDAY, 02 JANUARY 2023

START AT 7:30AM

Venue

3rd Floor, Sagarmatha hall-305

9. Web 3.0- Guest Lecture

WEB 3.0

Guest lecture

Mr. Ananda Nepal

Coordinator, Web System Development
The Kyoto College of Graduate Studies for Informatics, Japan

Sunday, 08 January 2023

START AT 09:30 AM

Participants:

All interested students.
(BSc.CSIT & BCA)

Picture 19: Faculty and Students workshop

Picture 20: Students attending guest lecture

Picture 21: Campus chief with Shinzo Kobayashi, NPO CCC-TIES, Nara, Japan and Nepal Ananda

Picture 22: Honoring and thanking with traditional 'khada'

Management Workshops

Presented By:

Parmeshwor Dahal

Aviation- Airport Services/Lecturer POM

Key features

- Interpersonal skill development ~
- Leadership skills ~
- Team building~
- SWOT Analysis ~
- Problem solving ~
- Corporate correspondance ~

BSc.CSIT

Participants: 2nd and 3rd Semester

Date: 8th, 15th, 22nd &
29th Magh 79

Venue: BSc. CSIT Hall

Workshop Schedule

Session

1

08th Magh'79

- Workshop Schedule Briefing
- Team formation
- Objective of Workshop
- Introduction to Interpersonal Skill Development
- Body posture & Communication skill
- Reasoning the image
- Quiz & Games

Session

2

15th Magh'79

- Introduction to Leadership
- Team Building
- Conflict Management and Problem solving
- Quiz & Games

Session

3

22th Magh'79

- SWOT Analysis
- Case Study of SWOT
- Corporate/Business Correspondence
- Quiz & Games

Session

4

29th Magh'79

- Presentation by each group (15 mins each)
- Speech by Seniors on their work experience
- Certificate distribution

Time: 11:00- 01:00 PM